

Total Protein Quantification Assay Kit Instruction

1. Reagent Composition and Preparation (100T/96 Samples)

Reagent I: 2 vials of powder and 2 bottles of diluent with 12.5mL each. Sealed and preserved at 4°C for 6 months.

Preparation of the reagent I solution: Dissolve each vial of powder with 1 bottle of diluent thoroughly and preserved at 4°C.

Reagent II: 2 vial of liquid with 250µL each. Sealed and preserved at 4°C for 6 months.

Preparation of the working solution: Mix reagent II and reagent I solution with the ratio of 1:50 (v/v) for the amount of solution needed.

Reagent III: 1 bottle of 20 ml stopping stock solution. Sealed and preserved at 4°C for 6 months.

Preparation of the stopping solution: Dilute the stock solution with double distilled water (DDW) to five times of its original volume. Preserved at 4°C.

Reagent IV: 1 vial of 0.2ml protein standard solution. Preserved at 4°C for 1 month or -20°C for 6 months.

2. Reagent Composition and Preparation (50T/48 Samples)

Reagent I, II and III are halved and reagent IV is the same compared to the 100T format.

3. Pretreatment

I. Animal tissue

Weigh the sample precisely and add saline with the ratio of 1:9 (g/mL). Homogenize the mixture in ice water bath and centrifuge at 2500 rpm for 10 min. Extract the supernatant and further dilute with saline to desired concentration for further measurement.

II. Plant tissue

Weigh the sample precisely and add saline or 0.1M PBS with the ratio of 1:9 (g/mL). Homogenize the mixture in ice water bath and centrifuge at 3500 rpm for 10 min. Extract the supernatant and further dilute with saline to desired concentration for further measurement.

III. Cultured Cells

Collected cells should be washed with isotonic once or twice (0.1M PBS or saline recommended). Centrifuge at 1000 rpm for 10 min and discard the supernatant. Mix the pellets with medium (0.1M PBS or saline recommended), and homogenize the mixture in ice water bath. The homogenate can be measured directly.

IV. Serum/Plasma

Can be measured directly.

V. Other fluid

Dilute the sample so that the protein concentration is in the range of 20-2000µg/mL. Pretest can be done to determine the dilution factor.

4. Procedures

Composition (μL)	Blank	Standard	Sample
Double Distilled Water	20		
563μg/ml Standard		20	
Sample			20
Working Solution	250	250	250
Mix and warm at 37°C for 30min			
Terminal Solution	750	750	750

Blend the solution and then set aside for 5min. Zero with the water and record the absorbed optical density (OD) of each tube at 562nm with 0.5cm light path.

5. Calculation Formula

$$C_{\text{protein}} \frac{\mu\text{g/ml}}{\mu\text{g/ml}} = \frac{OD_{\text{sample}} - OD_{\text{blank}}}{OD_{\text{standard}} - OD_{\text{blank}}} \times \frac{C_{\text{standard}}}{563\mu\text{g/ml}} \times \text{Dilution Factor}$$

6. Principle of the Assay

In base solution, cupric ion may be reduced to cuprous ion by protein and latter can be adducted with bicinchoninic acid (BCA) and the product has maximum light absorption at 562 nm which is proportion to the concentration of the product. Thus the concentration of protein can be calculated based on the absorbance of the solution.

7. Parameters of the kit

- I. Limitation: 20μg/ml
- II. Coefficient of Variation (CV) within a patch: 2.06%
- III. CV among patches: 4.72%
- IV. Recovery: 98.5%
- V. Linearity range: 20-2000μg/ml
- VI. Coefficient of determination: $r^2=0.999$

8. Features of the kit

Faster and Simpler than the classic Lowry method

High Sensitivity: Lowest detection limit is 0.5μg/ml and the lower bound of the linear range is 20μg/ml.

Least Chemical Interference: This method is compatible with most of the chemicals including 5% SDS, Triton X-100, Tween 20, 60 and 80.

Lower CV values: This method has CV values much lower than the CV values from Coomassie brilliant blue method.

Appendix I Standard Curve Establishment

1. Pretreatment

56.3 g/L protein standard solution is diluted to the following concentrations: 10000, 5000, 2500, 1000, 500, 250, 10, 50, 25, 0 μ g/mL.

2. Procedures

Composition (μ L)	Blank	Standard
Double Distilled Water	20	
563 μ g/ml Standard		20
Mix and warm at 37°C for 30min		
Working Solution	250	250
Terminal Solution	750	750

Blend the solution and then set aside for 5min. Zero with the water and record the absorbed optical density (OD) of each tube at 562nm with 0.5cm light path.

Note: The phenol standard and DDW volume values are listed with in μ l

3. Results

Concentration (μ g/ml)	OD Measured	Δ OD-OD _{Standard} -OD _{Blank}
0	0.015	0
25	0.02	0.005
50	0.025	0.01
100	0.036	0.021
250	0.067	0.052
500	0.119	0.104
1000	0.212	0.197
2500	0.514	0.499

Appendix II Assay Examples

I. For Serum

Human serum was diluted with saline to with the ratio of 1:99 (v/v). Mix thoroughly and the absorbance values were 0.011, 0.128 and 0.160 respectively.

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\text{protein}} \frac{\mu\text{g/ml}}{\mu\text{g/ml}} &= \frac{OD_{\text{sample}} - OD_{\text{blank}}}{OD_{\text{standard}} - OD_{\text{blank}}} \times C_{\text{standard}} \times \text{Dilution Factor} \\ &= \frac{0.160 - 0.011}{0.128 - 0.011} \times 563 \mu\text{g/ml} \times 100 = 7.17 \times 10^5 \mu\text{g/ml} \end{aligned}$$

II. For Animal Tissue

10% mouse renal tissue homogenate was diluted to 1% and measured. The absorbance values were 0.011, 0.128 and 0.201 respectively.

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\text{protein in 1\% homogenate}} \frac{\mu\text{g/ml}}{\mu\text{g/ml}} &= \frac{OD_{\text{sample}} - OD_{\text{blank}}}{OD_{\text{standard}} - OD_{\text{blank}}} \times C_{\text{standard}} \times \text{Dilution Factor} \\ &= \frac{0.201 - 0.011}{0.128 - 0.011} \times 563 \mu\text{g/ml} \times 1 = 9.14 \times 10^2 \mu\text{g/ml} \end{aligned}$$

10% mouse brain tissue homogenate was diluted to 1% and measured. The absorbance values were 0.011, 0.128 and 0.130 respectively.

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\text{protein in 1\% homogenate}} \frac{\mu\text{g/ml}}{\mu\text{g/ml}} &= \frac{OD_{\text{sample}} - OD_{\text{blank}}}{OD_{\text{standard}} - OD_{\text{blank}}} \times C_{\text{standard}} \times \text{Dilution Factor} \\ &= \frac{0.130 - 0.011}{0.128 - 0.011} \times 563 \mu\text{g/ml} \times 1 = 5.73 \times 10^2 \mu\text{g/ml} \end{aligned}$$

10% mouse muscle tissue homogenate was diluted to 1% and measured. The absorbance values were 0.011, 0.128 and 0.128 respectively.

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\text{protein in 1\% homogenate}} \frac{\mu\text{g/ml}}{\mu\text{g/ml}} &= \frac{OD_{\text{sample}} - OD_{\text{blank}}}{OD_{\text{standard}} - OD_{\text{blank}}} \times C_{\text{standard}} \times \text{Dilution Factor} \\ &= \frac{0.128 - 0.011}{0.128 - 0.011} \times 563 \mu\text{g/ml} \times 1 = 5.63 \times 10^2 \mu\text{g/ml} \end{aligned}$$

III. For Plant Tissue

Bok choy leaves were homogenized and diluted to 1% homogenate. The homogenate was measured and the absorbance values were 0.011, 0.128 and 0.098 respectively.

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\text{protein in 1\% homogenate}} \frac{\mu\text{g/ml}}{\mu\text{g/ml}} &= \frac{OD_{\text{sample}} - OD_{\text{blank}}}{OD_{\text{standard}} - OD_{\text{blank}}} \times C_{\text{standard}} \times \text{Dilution Factor} \\ &= \frac{0.098 - 0.011}{0.128 - 0.011} \times 563 \mu\text{g/ml} \times 1 = 4.19 \times 10^2 \mu\text{g/ml} \end{aligned}$$

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